

Kinetics and mechanism of periodate oxidation of *o*-anisidine in acetone-water medium

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Abstract : Main reaction product of the periodate oxidation of *o*-anisidine (OMA) in acetone-water medium is methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone. It was isolated and characterized. The kinetics of the reaction has been followed by monitoring the increase in the absorbance of reaction intermediate, C. Results under pseudo-first order conditions, [*o*-anisidine] >> [IO₄⁻], are in agreement with the rate law :

$$d[C]/dt = kK_w [S]_0 [IO_4^-] [H^+] / \{K_2 K_w + (K_w + K_b K_2) [H^+] + K_b [H^+]^2\}$$

where kK is the empirical composite rate constant, K_w is ionic product of water, K_2 is acid dissociation constant of H₄IO₆⁻, K_b is base dissociation constant of OMA and $[S]_0$ represents the concentration of OMA that has been taken in excess. In agreement with the rate law the $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ profile passes through the minimum. Increase in ionic strength increases the rate of reaction. Free radical scavengers do not affect the reaction rate. Thermodynamic parameters evaluated are : $E_a = 3.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $A = 25.9 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -54.1 \text{ cal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 2.4 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$.

Keywords : Kinetics, periodate oxidation, *o*-anisidine, methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.

Introduction

The kinetic studies reported for the non-Malpradian periodate oxidation of aromatic amines are rather few^{1-5} and are contradictory in regard to the ionic or free radical mechanism. Recent reports include the periodate oxidation of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine⁶ and oxidation of L-proline by bis(hydrogen periodato)argentate(III) complex anion⁷. In continuation to our earlier studies⁸⁻¹¹, the results of periodate oxidation of *o*-anisidine in acetone-water medium are being presented and discussed in the present communication.

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals :

Sodium meta periodate (Loba Chemie), *o*-anisidine (Sigma-Aldrich), acetone (E. Merck) and all other chemicals of analytical reagent/guaranteed reagent grade were used after redistillation/recrystallization. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer¹², consisting of different volumes of 0.05 M oxalic acid, 0.02 M boric acid, 0.05 M succinic acid, 0.05 M sodium sulphate and 0.05 M borax, was used for maintaining the pH, measured on Systronics

digital pH-meter-802. The reactions were studied in a spectrophotometric cell and initiated by adding temperature equilibrated NaIO₄ solution of known concentration to the reaction mixture containing the *o*-anisidine and buffer and maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1 °C).

Kinetics procedure :

The progress of the reaction was followed by recording the absorbance on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV Pharmaspec-1700), at 500 nm, i.e. the λ_{max} of the wine red color reaction mixture. λ_{max} was not found to change with change in pH. High precision thermostatically controlled water bath with an accuracy of ± 0.1 °C was employed for maintaining the desired temperature. Stock solutions of *o*-anisidine were prepared in acetone-water mixed solvent. For proper dissolution of *o*-anisidine and preventing the precipitation of reaction product during the period of study of kinetics, the acetone-water medium was used.

Product analysis :

Reaction mixture containing oxidant in excess was left overnight to ensure completion of the reaction. Initially the solution turned wine red, thereafter reddish brown

and finally the product was precipitated on standing. It was filtered and the filtrate was extracted with petroleum ether (40–60 °C). The extract was evaporated at room temperature to get a yellow colored compound which was found to be pure. It was recrystallized in chloroform and characterized as methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone on the basis of positive test for quinone¹³, m.p. 144 °C (lit. 145 °C¹⁴), UV spectrum in CHCl₃ giving absorption maxima at 250 and 352 nm, which suggested the presence of quinonoid structure in the compound (lit. 254 and 357 nm for methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone¹⁵). The IR spectrum of compound (in KBr) showed the presence of bands at 2971 (s) cm⁻¹ (due to ring C–H stretch), 1635 (s) cm⁻¹ (indicating the presence of C=O on 1,4-benzoquinone pattern with the possibility that the position of this band is lowered due to +I effect of methoxy group¹⁶), 3222 (s) cm⁻¹ (may be due to overtones of C=O stretch as the frequency is about twice that of C=O stretch). Further, the bands at 1393 (s) cm⁻¹, 1492 (s) cm⁻¹ may be due to C=C ring stretch. The bands at 1245 (m) cm⁻¹ to 1041 (m) cm⁻¹ may be due to asymmetric and symmetric C–O–C stretch and at 612 (s)(m) cm⁻¹ and 518 (s)(m) cm⁻¹ (due to out of plane C=C bending mode). The observed values are in good agreement with those reported/expected for methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.

The NMR spectrum of this compound in CDCl₃ showed

the peaks at δ 7.262 (1H, s); at 6.991 (2H, d) and at 4.084 (3H, s). A singlet at δ 4.084 may be due to -OCH₃ group attached to the ring. The other signals in spectrum at δ 7.262 and 6.991 were due to protons of the ring.

Stoichiometry :

Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing a known excess of NaIO₄ to react with substrate. After completion of the reaction, the precipitated product was filtered out and in the filtrate unconsumed NaIO₄ was determined iodometrically. The results indicate the stoichiometry to be 1 mol OMA : 2 moles periodate as in eq. (1),

Results

Preliminary observations :

On mixing the reactants, the solution becomes wine red which later changes in to reddish brown. On keeping for long time it finally gives the product. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final product. The rapid scan of the wine red solution showed the λ_{max} of the intermediate C to be 500 nm (Fig. 1). The UV-Visible spectra of IO₄⁻ and *o*-anisidine indicated these to show no absorption in visible region. Hence for following the kinetics

Fig. 1. Rapid UV-Vis scan of reaction solution at different time at $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{OMA}] = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 10% (v/v), Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 7.0.

the absorbance changes were recorded at 500 nm at which only the intermediate C absorbs. Plane mirror and Guggenheim's methods, respectively were used for evaluation of initial rates, (dC/dt), and pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} .

Rate law :

The kinetics was studied under pseudo order conditions, viz. $[IO_4^-]_0 \gg [S]$ and $[S]_0 \gg [IO_4^-]$. Under both these conditions the reaction is first order. Under the condition, $[S]_0 \gg [IO_4^-]$, the results (Table 1) were defined by the eq. (2) and pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was equal to $k_2 [S]_0$.

$$d[C]/dt = k_2 [IO_4^-] [S]_0 \quad (2)$$

where k_2 is a pH-dependent second order rate constant.

On the other hand under the condition $[IO_4^-]_0 \gg [S]$, the rate was defined by eq. (3) and k_{obs} was equal to $k_2 [IO_4^-]_0$.

$$d[C]/dt = k_2 [IO_4^-]_0 [S] \quad (3)$$

In eqs. (2) and (3) $[IO_4^-]_0$ and $[S]_0$ represent the initial concentrations of reactants in excess. The values of k_2 determined from k_{obs} values clearly indicate a clear cut first order in each of periodate and anisidine.

The effect of pH was examined in the range 5.0–9.0. Rate-pH profile indicates a maximum at pH 6.5 (Table 1), which could be due to change in the nature of species and their relative reactivity when the pH is changed.

Effect of ionic strength, free radical scavengers and temperature :

An increase in ionic strength, μ , led to an increase in the rate and the plot of $\log k_2$ versus μ was almost linear. This effect indicates an ion-dipole type interaction in the rate-determining step, and that the reacting ion is possibly an anion. Free radical scavengers acrylamide and allyl alcohol had no effect of on the reaction rate.

Table 1. Effect of variation of concentration of reactants, ionic strength and pH on the reaction rate

Temp. = 35 ± 0.1 °C						
[NaIO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	[OMA] (mol dm ⁻³)	Acetone (%)	[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	pH	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ (s ⁻¹)	$k_2 \times 10^2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.001	0.010	10	–	7.0	10.4	10.4
0.001	0.012	10	–	7.0	12.3	10.2
0.001	0.014	10	–	7.0	14.6	10.4
0.001	0.016	10	–	7.0	16.5	10.3
0.001	0.018	10	–	7.0	18.4	10.2
0.010	0.001	20	–	7.0	9.6	9.6
0.012	0.001	20	–	7.0	11.5	9.6
0.014	0.001	20	–	7.0	13.4	9.6
0.016	0.001	20	–	7.0	15.4	9.6
0.018	0.001	20	–	7.0	17.3	9.6
0.001	0.01	20	–	5.0	4.2	4.2
0.001	0.01	20	–	5.5	4.6	4.6
0.001	0.01	20	–	6.0	5.6	5.6
0.001	0.01	20	–	6.5	6.1	6.1
0.001	0.01	20	–	7.0	5.8	5.8
0.001	0.01	20	–	7.5	5.0	5.0
0.001	0.01	20	–	8.0	4.2	4.2
0.001	0.01	20	–	8.5	3.8	3.8
0.001	0.01	20	–	9.0	3.5	3.5
0.01	0.001	20	0.001	7.0	12.3	12.3
0.01	0.001	20	0.002	7.0	14.6	14.6
0.01	0.001	20	0.003	7.0	17.3	17.3
0.01	0.001	20	0.004	7.0	19.9	19.9

By determining the rate constants at four different temperatures (35.0 to 50.0 °C), the values of different thermodynamic parameters were found to be : $E_a = 3.1$ kcal mol⁻¹, $A = 25.9$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -54.1$ cal mol⁻¹, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 19.5$ kcal mol⁻¹ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 2.4$ kcal mol⁻¹ at [OMA] = 0.001 mol dm⁻³, [NaIO₄] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, pH = 7.0 and acetone = 10.0% (v/v).

Discussion

Some important features of this reaction, which provide clue to the possible mechanism, are as follows :

Firstly, there is an appearance of red-wine color which continues to darken with increase in the concentration of the intermediate, C and finally the product settles on standing for long time. Obviously, the colored intermediate is formed on a time scale of minutes and the final product on a time scale of hours. In reality the overall reaction involves several steps and possibly several transient intermediates, in addition to comparatively stable one C, are formed during the oxidation of *o*-anisidine into benzoquinone.

Secondly, the kinetic order of one in periodate but requirement of the two periodate molecules for each anisidine molecule as per stoichiometry indicates the involvement of only one periodate in the rate determining step and second IO₄⁻ ion is consumed in a fast reaction in the formation of the intermediate, C. It also indicates that the wine red colored intermediate is quite stable, and its concentration is not in steady state. Had this been so, there should have been no change in its concentration with time. On the contrary, concentration of C increases continuously with time and reaches a limiting value. And this been used in following the kinetics of this reaction.

Thirdly k_2 -pH profile indicates the presence of at least three differently reactive reactant species in the pH region chosen for study.

Before presenting a mechanism, it is necessary to discuss the speciation of anisidine and periodate species in aqueous solutions. In aqueous solutions, periodate exists in three forms governed by the equilibria :

The value of K_1 indicates that in the pH range 5–9 species H₅IO₆ shall be practically non-existent and hence only species H₄IO₆⁻ and H₃IO₆²⁻ are to be considered for explaining observed pH-dependence. In case of *o*-anisidine¹⁷, in aqueous solution the following acid-base equilibrium with $K_b = 3 \times 10^{-10}$ operates.

In the studied pH-range, both CH₃OC₆H₄NH₂ and CH₃OC₆H₄N⁺H₃ shall exist and both of these have been considered.

Based on the observed kinetic rate laws (2–3) and pH-dependence, the following mechanism, which assumes, CH₃OC₆H₄NH₂ and H₄IO₆⁻ to be the reactive species, is proposed.

The intermediate, C, appear to undergo very slow reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction product.

In the mechanism for simplicity, H₄IO₆⁻ has been written as IO₄⁻. Since the elementary reactions in liquid phase are rare, the formation of a transient intermediate [C], which could be a collisional complex/reactant pair in a rapid step having a low value of equilibrium constant, K , is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism.

The mechanistic steps (8–9) lead to the rate law :

$$d[\text{C}]/dt = k [\text{A}] \quad (11)$$

$$= kK [\text{CH}_3\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2] [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (12)$$

Since the observed kinetics shows first order in each of [CH₃OC₆H₄NH₂] and [IO₄⁻], the value of K must be low.

At affixed pH, under the condition $[\text{S}]_0 \gg [\text{IO}_4^-]$, the rate of formation of intermediate, C, is given by eq. (13),

$$d[C]/dt = kK [IO_4^-] [S]_0 / (1 + K [S]_0) \quad (13)$$

Likewise, under the condition $[IO_4^-]_0 \gg [S]$

$$d[C]/dt = kK [IO_4^-]_0 [S] / (1 + K [IO_4^-]_0) \quad (14)$$

Since the reaction shows a first order in each of $[S]$ and $[IO_4^-]$, the inequalities $K [S]_0 \ll 1$ and $K [IO_4^-]_0 \ll 1$ should operate in eqs. (13) and (14), respectively leading to the rate laws in eqs. (2) and (3).

On substituting the values of concentrations of the reactive species $[CH_3OC_6H_4NH_2]$ and $[IO_4^-]$ in terms of equilibria (4-5) and (6), respectively, in eq. (12), the complete rate law including $[H^+]$ -dependence becomes :

$$d[C]/dt = kK \left\{ \frac{[S]_0 [OH^-]}{[OH^-] + K_b} \right\} \left\{ \frac{[IO_4^-] [H^+]}{K_2 + [H^+]} \right\} \quad (15)$$

On replacing the term $[OH^-] [H^+]$ by K_w and $[OH^-]$ by $K_w/[H^+]$ in denominator and on rearranging, we get,

$$d[C]/dt = kKK_w [S]_0 [IO_4^-] [H^+] / \{ K_2 K_w + (K_w + K_b K_2) [H^+] + K_b [H^+]^2 \} \quad (16)$$

On comparing eqs. (2) and (16), we get

$$k_2 = kKK_w [H^+] / \{ K_2 K_w + (K_w + K_b K_2) [H^+] + K_b [H^+]^2 \} \quad (17)$$

Eq. (17) on rearranging becomes eq. (18).

$$1/k_2 = (K_2/kK [H^+] + \{ (K_w + K_b K_2)/kKK_w \} + K_b [H^+]/kKK_w) \quad (18)$$

The nature of the rate law shows that a plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ shall pass through a minimum as discussed in detail in a review by Gupta and Gupta¹⁸. On differentiating $1/k_2$ with respect to $[H^+]$ in eq. (18), we get the values of $d(1/k_2)/d[H^+]$ and $d^2[1/k_2]/d[H^+]^2$. The value of second derivative is found to be positive showing the plot of $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ to pass through a minimum. Thus, on setting $d[1/k_2]/d[H^+] = 0$ for obtaining hydrogen ion concentration at which the $1/k_2$ vs $[H^+]$ profile will pass through minimum, we obtain,

$$[H^+]_{\min} = (K_2 K_w / K_b)^{1/2}$$

On substituting the values of K_2 , K_w and K_b , we get

$$[H^+]_{\min} = 3.8 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

It is worth to note that the calculated value of $[H^+]_{\min}$ is

in excellent agreement with the experimental value of $[H^+]_{\min}$ of $3.16 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ obtained from $1/k_2$ versus $[H^+]$ plot (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Effect of $[H^+]$ on reaction rate at $[NaIO_4] = 0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[OMA] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 10% (v/v). Temp. = $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

It is necessary and interesting to discuss the possible molecular mechanism of the reaction. Mechanism proposed in Scheme 1 shows the first step as a reversible bimolecular reaction between OMA and $[IO_4^-]$. The formation of a charged intermediate complex [A] taking place by the attack of $[IO_4^-]$ on the nitrogen of anilino group and stabilization of positive charge on this nitrogen are well supported by our earlier LFER studies on this type of reaction series¹⁹. The high negative value of entropy of activation supports the involvement of solvation effects in this reaction. The formation of another intermediate [B] followed by its reaction with another IO_4^- to form quinoneimine [C] in a fast step are the expected steps of the mechanism involved.

The last step (10) seems to be the slow hydrolysis and rearrangement of (C) to give methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone

Scheme 1

(D), i.e. the main product of the reaction that has been isolated, separated and characterized.

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